

About the second Droz-Farny circle

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In this article, we prove the theorem relative to the *second Droz-Farny circle*, and a sentence that generalizes it. The paper [1] informs that the following *Theorem* is attributed to J. Neuberg (*Mathesis*, 1911).

First Theorem. The circles with its centers in the middles of triangle ABC passing through its orthocenter H intersect the sides BC , CA and AB respectively in the points A_1, A_2, B_1, B_2 and C_1, C_2 , situated on a concentric circle with the circle circumscribed to the triangle ABC (**the second Droz-Farny circle**).

Proof. We denote by M_1, M_2, M_3 the middles of ABC triangle's sides, see *Figure 1*. Because $AH \perp M_2M_3$ and H belongs to the circles with centers in M_2 and M_3 , it follows that AH is the radical axis of these circles, therefore we have $AC_1 \cdot AC_2 = AB_2 \cdot AB_1$. This relation shows that B_1, B_2, C_1, C_2 are concyclic points, because the center of the circle on which they are situated is O , the center of the circle circumscribed to the triangle ABC , hence we have that:

Figure 1

$$OB_1 = OC_1 = OC_2 = OB_2 \quad (1).$$

Analogously, O is the center of the circle on which the points A_1, A_2, C_1, C_2 are situated, hence:

$$OA_1 = OC_1 = OC_2 = OA_2 \quad (2).$$

Also, O is the center of the circle on which the points A_1, A_2, B_1, B_2 are situated, and therefore:

$$OA_1 = OB_1 = OB_2 = OA_2 \quad (3).$$

The relations (1), (2), (3) show that the points $A_1, A_2, B_1, B_2, C_1, C_2$ are situated on a circle having the center in O , called *the second Droz-Farny circle*.

Proposition. The radius of the second Droz-Farny circle is given by:

$$R_2^2 = 5e^2 - \frac{1}{2}(a^2 + b^2 + c^2).$$

Proof. From the right triangle OM_1A_1 , using Pitagora theorem, it follows that:

$$OA_1^2 = OM_1^2 + A_1M_1^2 = OM_1^2 + M_1M_2.$$

From the triangle BHC , using the median theorem, we have:

$$HM_1^2 = \frac{1}{4}[2(BH^2 + CH^2) - BC^2].$$

But in a triangle, $AH = 2OM_1, BH = 2OM_2, CH = 2OM_3$, hence:

$$HM_1^2 = 2OM_2^2 + 2OM_3^2 = \frac{a^2}{4}.$$

But $OM_1^2 = R^2 - \frac{a^2}{4}$; $OM_2^2 = R^2 - \frac{b^2}{4}$; $OM_3^2 = R^2 - \frac{c^2}{4}$, where R is the radius of the circle circumscribed to the triangle ABC .

We find that $OA_1^2 = R_2^2 = 5R^2 - \frac{1}{2}(a^2 + b^2 + c^2)$.

Remarks.

1. We can compute $OM_1^2 + M_1M_2$ using the median theorem in the triangle OM_1H for the median M_1O_9 (O_9 is the center of the nine points circle, i.e. the middle of (OH)). Because $O_9M_1 = \frac{1}{2}R$, we obtain: $R_2^2 = \frac{1}{2}(OM^2 + R^2)$. In this way, we can prove the *Theorem* computing OB_1^2 and OC_1^2 .
2. The statement of the *First Theorem* was the subject no. 1 of the 49th International Olympiad in Mathematics, held at Madrid in 2008.
3. The *First Theorem* can be proved in the same way for an obtuse triangle, but it is obvious that for a right triangle, the second Droz-Farny circle coincides with the circle circumscribed to the triangle ABC .
4. The *First Theorem* appears as proposed problem in [2].

Second Theorem. The three pairs of points determined by the intersections of each circle with the center in the middle of triangle's side with the respective side are on a circle if and only these circles have as radical center the triangle's orthocenter.

Proof. Let M_1, M_2, M_3 the middles of the sides of triangle ABC and let $A_1, A_2, B_1, B_2, C_1, C_2$ the intersections with BC, CA, AB respectively of the circles with centers in M_1, M_2, M_3 .

Let us suppose that $A_1, A_2, B_1, B_2, C_1, C_2$ are concyclic points. The circle on which they are situated has evidently the center in O , the center of the circle

circumscribed to the triangle ABC . The radical axis of the circles with centers M_2, M_3 will be perpendicular on the line of centers M_2M_3 , and because A has equal powers in relation to these circles, since $AB_1 \cdot AB_2 = AC_1 \cdot AC_2$, it follows that the radical axis will be the perpendicular taken from A on M_2M_3 , i.e. the height from A of triangle ABC .

Furthermore, it ensues that the radical axis of the circles with centers in M_1 and M_2 is the height from B of triangle ABC and consequently the intersection of the heights, hence the orthocenter H of the triangle ABC is the radical center of the three circles.

Reciprocal. If the circles having the centers in M_1, M_2, M_3 have the orthocenter with the radical center, it follows that the point A , being situated on the height from A which is the radical axis of the circles of centers M_2, M_3 will have equal powers in relation to these circles and, consequently, $AB_1 \cdot AB_2 = AC_1 \cdot AC_2$, a relation that implies that B_1, B_2, C_1, C_2 are concyclic points, and the circle on which these points are situated has O as its center. Similarly, $BA_1 \cdot BA_2 = BC_1 \cdot BC_2$, therefore A_1, A_2, C_1, C_2 are concyclic points on a circle of center O . Having $OB_1 = OB_2 = OC_1 = OC_2$ and $OA_1 \cdot OA_2 = OC_1 \cdot OC_2$, we get that the points $A_1, A_2, B_1, B_2, C_1, C_2$ are situated on a circle of center O .

Remarks.

1. The *First Theorem* is a particular case of the *Second Theorem*, because the three circles of centers M_1, M_2, M_3 pass through H , which means that H is their radical center.
2. The Problem 525 from [3] drives us to the following *Proposition* that provides the way to construct the circles of centers M_1, M_2, M_3 that intersect the sides in points that belong to a Droz-Farny circle of type 2.

Proposition. The circles $C\left(M_1, \frac{1}{2}\sqrt{k+a^2}\right)$, $C\left(M_2, \frac{1}{2}\sqrt{k+b^2}\right)$, $C\left(M_3, \frac{1}{2}\sqrt{k+c^2}\right)$ intersect the sides BC, CA, AB respectively in six concyclic points; k is a conveniently chosen constant, and a, b, c are the lengths of the sides of triangle ABC .

Proof. According to the *Second Theorem*, it is necessary to prove that the orthocenter H of triangle ABC is the radical center for the circles from hypothesis.

The power of H in relation with $C\left(M_1, \frac{1}{2}\sqrt{k+a^2}\right)$ is equal to $HM_1^2 - \frac{1}{4}(k+a^2)$. We observed that $M_1^2 = 4R^2 - \frac{b^2}{2} - \frac{c^2}{2} - \frac{a^2}{4}$, therefore $HM_1^2 - \frac{1}{4}(k+a^2) = 4R^2 - \frac{a^2+b^2+c^2}{4} - \frac{1}{4}k$. We use the same expression

for the power of H in relation to the circles of centers M_2, M_3 , hence H is the radical center of these three circles.

Bibliography.

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